

SITE GPR	YEAR 2010	AREA B	SECTOR	ELEVATION Min: 62.0849 Max: 62.5272	STRATIGRAPHICAL UNIT 1221 <input type="checkbox"/> Natural <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Anthropic	Tabu Project														
In cross-section? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		In elevation drawing? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No		Photos: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No #: 784-793	Photo Model: <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No #:															
DEFINITION Soil in square channel				Covered by <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1230	Fills <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> SU: 1228	Filled by <input type="checkbox"/> SU:														
HOW IS LAYER DISTINGUISHED? <input type="checkbox"/> Color <input type="checkbox"/> Composition <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Compaction		FORMATION PROCESS <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Accumulation <input type="checkbox"/> Construction <input type="checkbox"/> Cutting <input type="checkbox"/> Erosion <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse <input type="checkbox"/> Intentional deposition																		
INCLUSIONS For each inclusion specify frequency: (f)requent, (m)edium, (r)are					SOIL/MATRIX clay 20% silt 80% sand ___%															
Anthropic		Geological		Organic																
<input type="checkbox"/> Pottery <input type="checkbox"/> Nails <input type="checkbox"/> Tiles <input type="checkbox"/> Marble <input type="checkbox"/> Amphorae <input type="checkbox"/> Quarried debris <input type="checkbox"/> Dolia <input type="checkbox"/> Slag <input type="checkbox"/> Brick <input type="checkbox"/> Mosaic tile(s) <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt slabs <input type="checkbox"/> Mortar <input type="checkbox"/> Opus signinum <input type="checkbox"/> Coins <input type="checkbox"/> Painted plaster <input type="checkbox"/> Metal (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Burnt Adobe <input type="checkbox"/> Collapse debris <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Glass		<input type="checkbox"/> Tufo (specify) <input type="checkbox"/> Travertine <input type="checkbox"/> Other Limestone <input type="checkbox"/> Basalt <input type="checkbox"/> Clay <input type="checkbox"/> Sand <input type="checkbox"/> Silt <input type="checkbox"/> Pebbles (range) <input type="checkbox"/> Gravel (range)		<input type="checkbox"/> Charcoal <input type="checkbox"/> Ash <input type="checkbox"/> Animal bones <input type="checkbox"/> Human bones <input type="checkbox"/> Animal teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Human teeth <input type="checkbox"/> Shells <input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)																
					<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Granular <input type="checkbox"/> Layered <input type="checkbox"/> Cohesive															
					<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Compaction</td> <td>Color</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Hard</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Compact</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Friable</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loose</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red</td> </tr> <tr> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Soft</td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow</td> </tr> <tr> <td></td> <td><input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)</td> </tr> </table>		Compaction	Color	<input type="checkbox"/> Hard	<input type="checkbox"/> Black <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Compact	<input type="checkbox"/> Gray <input type="checkbox"/> Light Brown	<input type="checkbox"/> Friable	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Gray <input type="checkbox"/> White	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Loose	<input type="checkbox"/> Yellow <input type="checkbox"/> Red	<input type="checkbox"/> Soft	<input type="checkbox"/> Light Yellow		<input type="checkbox"/> Other (specify)
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UNIT LIMITS (also indicate on overlay)																				
Northern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit		Depth: <input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original																
Southern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit																		
Western Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit																		
Eastern Limit		<input type="checkbox"/> Original <input type="checkbox"/> Not Original <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Excavation Limit																		
STRATIGRAPHICAL SEQUENCE																				
Is equal to:			Is bound to (only for masonry):																	
Is abutted by:			Abuts:																	
Is covered by: 1230			Covers:																	
Is cut by:			Cuts:																	
Is filled by:			Fills: 1228																	
OBSERVATIONS Fill within square channel 1228, not excavated																				
DESCRIPTION Position within sector: SW-corner of Trench B Shape: square according to surrounding architecture																				
For layers complete this section: Surface (slope direction; visible inclusions): no slope Observations about inclusions (Clusters? Deposition slope) no clusters observed Observations about thickness (Increases? Decreases?): no information Nature of the interface with layer below: <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> diffuse <input type="checkbox"/> commingled <input type="checkbox"/> other (specify)																				
For cuts complete this section: Cut edges: <input type="checkbox"/> rounded <input type="checkbox"/> straight Cut sides: <input type="checkbox"/> straight <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> convex <input type="checkbox"/> sloping Cut bottom: <input type="checkbox"/> flat <input type="checkbox"/> concave <input type="checkbox"/> irregular How is cut top edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded How is cut bottom edge? <input type="checkbox"/> sharp <input type="checkbox"/> rounded Observations:			Sketch for layers and/or cuts (indicate North): see SU sheet 1228																	

For structural remains complete this section

Alignment:

Building Technique: Adobe/Mud-brick Ashlar (blocks) irregular (unworked) stone Concrete Other (specify)

Binding Agent: None Clay Mortar (if so, specify composition, color, compaction)

Concrete inclusions:

Material Tufo Basalt Travertine Tiles Other (specify)

Size Small (range) _____ Medium (range) _____ Large (range) _____ Representative size: e.g. 2 x 1 x 2 cmz

Wall Facing:

Opus quadratum Opus incertum Opus reticulatum Petit appareil Opus testaceum Opus mixtum Opus vittatum Other (specify)

Complete this section for foundations Faced foundation Wooden shuttering No shuttering

floor/revetment type

Floor type: Beaten Earth Opus signinum Opus scutulatum Opus Sectile Mosaic Opus spicatum Other (specify)

Wall finishing Stucco Opus signinum Plaster Painted Plaster Other (specify)

Approx. length, width, height of structural remains:

Description:

Sketch (if applicable, indicate North)

INTERPRETATION

soil (which has only been seen from above)
 rich has accumulated within the square channel 1228
 and was too deep to be reached by excavation
 this year

SOIL SAMPLING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

NON SOIL SAMPLES: Yes No

If yes, specify (e.g. charcoal, mortar etc.):

Size:

SIEVING: Yes No

Total volume of layer (buckets):

Sample quantity (buckets):

Sample fraction (%):

STRATIGRAPHICAL RELIABILITY

Good Fair Poor

Filled-out by	CMM	on	23.07.2010
Revised by	CMM	on	26.07.2010
PDFd by	JJM	on	27.07.2010
Entered by		on	